

THE REACTION OF SOME AROMATIC DIAMINES WITH ETHYL MALONATE.

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The reaction of ethyl malonate with various monoamines gives malonamides and malonamates according to the conditions of the reaction (Whitely, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 24). Since in the case of diamines the number of products expected will be greater, a study of the reaction of malonic ester with benzidine, tolidine and *p*-phenylenediamine has been undertaken varying (i) the concentrations of the ester and base, (ii) the temperature of the reaction and, (iii) the medium of reaction.

By reacting malonic and succinic acids with *o*- and *p*-phenylenediamines, Meyer (*Annalen*, 1903, 327, 1) isolated various products, *e.g.*, *o*-phenylene-succinamide, *N*:*N'*-di-*o*-aminophenylsuccinamide, *o*-phenylene-amidine-succinic acid and *p*-phenylene-disuccinimide. Later, the same author (*Annalen*, 1906, 347, 17) prepared diethyl *p*-phenylenedimalonamate by reacting *p*-phenylenediamine with malonic ester. Malonylbenzidine, $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2$, was obtained by Ramfrey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 621) by heating malonic ester with benzidine at 210°.

The reaction between equimolecular proportions of ethyl malonate and benzidine at 140-60° yielded two substances melting above 300°. On increasing the proportion of ester and lowering the reaction temperature to 115-120°, the reaction product was found to consist of ethyl 4-aminodiphenyl-4'-malonamate $\text{H}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ (I), diethyl diphenylene-4 : 4'-dimalonamate $(-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et})_2$ (II), and malonylbenzidine (III). The presence of the amino group in compound (I) was proved by diazotising it and coupling with β -naphthol. The compound (II), containing free ester groups, underwent hydrolysis to the corresponding acid which on decarboxylation gave diacetylbenzidine. The compound (I), on heating at 140° for about 4 hours, gave the compounds (II), (III) and benzidines while on boiling with xylene for about 10 hours passed exclusively into (III). The results of comparative yields from the experiments carried out with different proportions of the reacting substances at different temperatures are given in Table I (*vide* experimental).

In the case of tolidine only two compounds could be isolated corresponding to types (II) and (III) from benzidine, although this reaction was carried out at lower temperatures and with excess of ester.

The reaction of malonic ester with *p*-phenylenediamine gave (i) diethyl *p*-phenylene-dimalonamate (IV), (ii) ethyl *p*-acetaminophenylenemalonamate (V) and an insoluble blue mass. The same reactants after 12 hours' boiling in xylene gave the compounds (IV) and (V), while if the heating was continued for 24 hours, the resulting mass gave only (V) and an insoluble residue. The compound (IV) on heating at 160° for about 4 hours gave the compound (V) and *p*-acetaminophenylenemalonimide (VI),

while in boiling xylene only compound (V) was obtained. The compounds (IV) and (V), which on heating at 180-85° also passed into compound (VI), on hydrolysis gave their respective acids which on decarboxylation furnished diacetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Reaction of Ethyl Malonate with Benzidine.—A mixture of ethyl malonate (0.3 mol.) and benzidine (0.1 mol.) was heated in an oil-bath at 115-20° for 8 hours allowing the alcohol formed to distil over. The reaction product after cooling was filtered, washed with alcohol to remove the unreacted ester and amine, and then repeatedly extracted with boiling alcohol and filtered hot leaving a residue (A). The filtrate on cooling deposited shining plates of diethyl diphenylene-4:4'-dimalonamate (II). The filtrates from (II) on concentration and dilution with equal amount of water yielded ethyl 4-aminodiphenyl-4'-malonamate (I), which is very soluble in cold alcohol, sparingly soluble in benzene and practically insoluble in petroleum, ether and water, m. p. 139-40°. (Found: C, 68.2; H, 6.2; N, 9.2. C₁₇H₁₈O₃N₂ requires C, 68.4; H, 6.0; N, 9.4 per cent).

Azo Derivative.—Ethyl 4-aminodiphenyl-4'-malonamate was diazotised and coupled with β -naphthol as usual. The colouring matter on recrystallisation from alcohol was obtained as bright red shining plates, m. p. 298° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.2. C₂₇H₂₃O₄N₃ requires N, 9.2 per cent).

Ethyl 4-aminodiphenyl-4'-malonamate was heated in an oil-bath at 140° for about 4 hours. The resulting mass on extraction with boiling alcohol gave (i) a residue insoluble in alcohol, (ii) diethyl diphenylene-4:4'-dimalonamate (II) (*vide infra*). (Found: N, 7.0 per cent) and, (iii) some benzidine.

Diethyl diphenylene-4:4'-dimalonamate (II) is sparingly soluble in hot alcohol and practically insoluble in cold alcohol, benzene, petroleum, ether, etc, m. p. above 300°. (Found: C, 64.1; H, 5.9; N, 6.8. C₂₂H₂₄O₆N₂ requires C, 64.0; H, 5.8; N, 6.8 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Diethyl diphenylene-4:4'-dimalonamate (II).—The above mentioned compound was refluxed on the water-bath with the calculated amount of alcoholic sodium hydroxide. When the reaction was complete (about 1 hour) the solution was filtered hot and acidified when the free acid separated out. It was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in which it was very sparingly soluble, m.p. 323-24° (decomp.). It is practically insoluble in water, alcohol, benzene, petroleum and ether. The sodium salt of the acid was crystallised from water. (Found: N, 6.7; Na, 11.5. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6N_2Na_2$ requires N, 7.0; Na, 11.5 per cent). The free acid was decarboxylated at 300° to diacetylbenzidine, m.p. 317°.

Malonylbenzidine (III).—The residue (A) is practically insoluble in all ordinary organic solvents except in boiling nitrobenzene in which it is very sparingly soluble, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 5.0; N, 10.8. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires C, 71.4; H, 4.8; N, 11.1 per cent).

Ethyl 4-aminodiphenyl-4'-malonamate (I) was also heated in boiling xylene for about 10 hours. The resulting mass was filtered, washed with petroleum to remove xylene, dried and then repeatedly extracted with boiling alcohol. Nothing separated from alcoholic filtrates. The insoluble residue was identified to be malonylbenzidine. (Found: N, 11.3. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.1 per cent).

TABLE I.

Comparative Yields of Compounds I, II and III from Experiments carried out with different Proportions of Ethyl malonate and Benzidine at different Temperatures.

Benzidine.	Malonic ester.	Temp.	Yields of compounds		
			I.	II.	III.
18.4 g. (0.1 mol.)	32.0 g. (0.2 mol.)	120-25°	2 g.	7 g.	17 g.
18.4 (0.1 mol.)	48.0 (0.3 mol.)	120-25°	6.5	9.1	9.1
18.4 (0.1 mol.)	48.0 (0.3 mol.)	115-120°	8.4	5.5	3.3

Reaction of Ethyl Malonate with Tolidine.

A mixture of ethyl malonate (0.3 mols) and tolidine (0.1 mol.) was heated as in the first experiment at 120° for about 6 hours. The reaction product was then filtered, washed with little alcohol to remove unreacted base and ester and then extracted several times with boiling alcohol. The filtrates on cooling deposited diethyl di-*o*-tolyl-4:4'-dimalonamate. Nothing separated from filtrates either on dilution with water or on evaporation, thus indicating the absence of the compound of type (I). The residue left after

extraction with boiling alcohol was practically insoluble in the usual organic solvents. *Diethyl di-o-tolyl-4:4'-dimalonamate* is sparingly soluble in boiling alcohol, practically insoluble in cold alcohol, benzene, petroleum, ether, m. p. above 300°. (Found: C, 65·6; H, 6·7; N, 6·7. $C_{24}H_{28}O_8N_2$ requires C, 65·4; H, 6·4; N, 7·4 per cent).

Reaction of Ethyl Malonate with p-Phenylenediamine.—A mixture of ethyl malonate (0·3 mol.) and *p*-phenylenediamine (0·1 mol.) was heated at 115–120° for about 10 hours and the product on working up as usual yielded (i) ethyl *p*-acetaminophenylmalonamate (V). (ii) ethyl *p*-phenylene-dimalonamate (IV), and (iii) a blue powder practically insoluble in usual organic solvents (Found: N, 13·9 per cent). On carrying out the reaction in presence of xylene at 140–50° for 12 hours, the compounds (IV) and (V) with traces of (VI) were obtained; on prolonging the heating to 24 hours only the compound (V) with traces of (VI) could be obtained.

Hydrolysis of Diethyl p-phenylenedimalonamate (IV).—Ethyl *p*-phenylene-dimalonamate (IV) on hydrolysis with the calculated amount (1·2 mol.) of alcoholic sodium hydroxide yielded the corresponding acid which when heated began to turn black above 250°, shrink at 280° and melt with decomposition at about 300°. (Found: N, 9·9; M.W., 280·3. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6N_2$ requires N, 10·0 per cent. M.W., 280·0). This acid on decarboxylation gave diacetyl *p*-phenylenediamine, m.p. 204°.

Action of Heat on Diethyl p-Phenylenedimalonamate.—Ethyl *p*-phenylene-dimalonamate was heated in an oil-bath at 160° for about 4 hours and the resulting mass with an ester-like odour on working up as usual gave (i) a residue insoluble in alcohol and other organic solvents (Found: C, 60·8; H, 4·7; N, 12·8. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires C, 60·6; H, 4·6; N, 12·9 per cent). (ii) *p*-acetaminophenylmalonimide (VI), and (iii) ethyl *p*-acetaminophenyl malonamate (Found: C, 59·1; H, 6·0; N, 10·6 per cent).

Ethyl p-acetaminophenyl-malonamate (V) is sparingly soluble in boiling alcohol and practically insoluble in cold alcohol, benzene, petroleum and ether, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 59·0; H, 6·0; N, 10·5. $C_{13}H_{16}O_4N_2$ requires C, 59·1; H, 6·0; N, 10·6 per cent). On hydrolysis with the calculated amount of alcoholic sodium hydroxide as usual, the corresponding acid, practically insoluble in the usual organic solvents, was obtained, m.p. about 300° (decomp.) with shrinking at 280°. (Found: N, 11·7. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 11·9 per cent).